

METHODS OF DIRECTING FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS TO THE PROFESSION THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF THEIR ARTISTIC AND CREATIVE COMPETENCE ON THE BASIS OF THE ARTPEDAGOGICAL APPROACH

Madina Nurullaevna Nasritdinova

Teacher of the department of Musical education and culture of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7980320>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the current problems of future music education teachers, such as the need to develop their creativity and professional competence through the means of art pedagogy, which is a form of modern education today and is recognized as a field of pedagogy.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, art pedagogy, modern educational tool, musical education, perception, thinking, knowledge, skills, model, modern educational style.*

The time has already changed, and its demands are growing along with it, while the form and methods of education remain the same. Of course, all new trends are built on the foundation, i.e., the old one, but its perfection lies in the mobilization of education based on the order of time and society.

Art pedagogy summarizes theory and practice, provides the development of the theory and practice of the process of artistic development of people and the formation of the foundations of personal culture through art and artistic-creative activities.

Such a crisis situation of the new Uzbekistan society requires, first of all, to review the fundamental foundations of the education of the young generation, that is, children and students. These social groups are the object of national-state interests, as they are a strategic resource that ensures the future of our country, its development, and the continuity of its historical and cultural heritage.

The educational importance of the above-mentioned youth periods is characterized by a state of intensive socialization, formation of a value system, stable personal qualities and self-awareness.

It is enough for children and adolescents to recognize the personality of the teacher and his professionalism, and they have the ability to quickly adapt to the goal-oriented educational process. Therefore, these social groups are traditionally defined as the main object of teachers' professional activity. All educational effects are based on the fact that they are directed to the minds of students and that the reactions of a person to the external environment are necessarily derivatives that determine his thinking.

Consequently, the problem of moral education of school-aged children is particularly relevant in connection with the modern socio-cultural situation, which is described by scientists as a state of global spiritual and moral crisis.

It is not without reason that interest in the semantic field of personality is increasing in pedagogy and psychology. The first attempt to reveal the meaning of the concept of "meaning" was made by A.N. Made by Leontiev[1]. According to the scientist, the meaning is manifested as a relation to the purpose of the activity motive.

Formation of the theory and practice of education and development of moral qualities of younger schoolchildren along with their artistic and creative abilities - a study by scientists from the CIS countries H.Kh. Batchaeva, O.S. Bogdanova, L.I. Bozhovich, V.V. Lyublinskaya, B.S. Mukhina, D. B. Elkosh, Yu. K. Yaglovskaya and others became an object. According to Z. T. Hasanov, D. V. Grigorev, I. I. Zaretskaya, D. M. Mallayev, A. Y. Smetanina, E. V. Taranova and other researchers, the cause of youth indifference comes from alienation from culture as a way of preserving and conveying values, and this leads to a change in the concept of good and evil in the young generation. According to Y.P.Azarov, A.S.Gordin, V.I.Petrova, E.A.Yamburg, there is a scientific position in which the active obsessive propaganda of popular culture is considered as a factor that helps to create a "society of complete alienation" devoid of cultural monuments.

According to V.V.Abramenkova, B.C.Bezrukova, D.G.Levchuk, S.G.Jakobson and others, the approach to moral education, taking into account the reality of modern society, the direction of research is much weaker than mental, physical and other types of education.

V.P. Anisymov, S.S. Brikunov, O.S. Bulatova, E.A. Medvedeva, C.B. Starikova, Y.S. Shevchenko, N.Y. Shumakova and others paid attention to the moral possibilities of art in educating schoolchildren. N.Y.Sergeyeva, J.S.Valeyeva used creative methods in the form of artistic pedagogy in their research on socialization of the individual and professional training of the future teacher. The main tools of artistic pedagogy in the formation of professional preparation of teachers for patriotic education are reflected in the research of MV Guzeyev.

Nevertheless, according to the analysis of the unpleasant realities in social life and statistical data, it is noted that the educational possibilities of art are not fully used in the practice of school activities.

The emergence of art pedagogy as a new direction of the integration of pedagogy and art has expanded the possibilities of realizing tasks. Accordingly, the problems of considering art pedagogy as a scientific-pedagogical direction based on the integration of the educational influence of several types of art on the individual, the main mechanism of which is the emotional perception of artistic images, the social experience concentrated in art mastery becomes relevant.

The introduction of art pedagogy in the development of the creative competence of future music education teachers, the ability to fully use its possibilities, the development of the thinking of the growing youth of New Uzbekistan, the awareness of the realities in the environment it allows to acquire necessary life knowledge, such as being able to form a personal relationship.

The development of effective pedagogical conditions and technologies for the use of art pedagogical means in educating the creative abilities of young people, as well as the substantiation of experience, a certain algorithm of subjective interaction and its application in the educational process of elementary school students, is an ethical method of art pedagogy, it provides for the development of an education model and the implementation of the program .

Art pedagogy or the educational process through the medium of art is an innovative pedagogical technology that contributes to the creation of an emotionally rich environment for the formation of free moral relations of children, a non-traditional approach to influencing a person using art.

The essence of art pedagogy is to educate and develop the personality of the student through the means of art, to master the basics of artistic culture, and to acquire practical skills in the types of artistic activity.

The purpose of art pedagogy:

- activation of students' cognitive activity through artistic means;
- development of emotional memory and creative imagination;
- strive to harmonize the spiritual and moral state of the human inner world;
- ensuring the child's personal socialization and self-identification in the process of familiarization with national and world art;
 - culture and art expressed in national music, visual art, literature, sculpture, singing, theater, choreography, examples of intangible culture, etc. to develop love for children, etc.

In addition, it is certain that all functions of culture and art have a therapeutic effect on the developing personality of the child. It is necessary to take into account the different effects of each type of art on children, which is determined by their developmental characteristics. Currently, art pedagogy is studying the positive effects of exposure to children with various developmental disabilities of different ages.

At the same time, it is possible to use a number of means of movement, such as dance, visual arts, music, and improvisational means of summarizing the moral qualities of the student's personality through the means of art pedagogy. Expressive art tools allow children to be influenced at a subconscious level, which in turn creates the basis for students to think creatively, express their ideas and emotional reactions.

Art pedagogy is essentially an integrative field of knowledge, because it combines the content, technology, and pedagogical methods and tools of artistic activity. The subject of our research is aimed at using the opportunities of art pedagogy in the education of moral qualities of elementary school students in a certain department of art pedagogy.

Using the possibilities of art pedagogy allows you to find a way to help restore harmony in the emotional world of the child, to form his thinking and self-esteem, so that the child has the opportunity to enter the world of adults.

Functions of art pedagogy:

- educational, that is, a person who understands reality through art becomes mature. Ensuring the acquisition of knowledge in the field of art and practical skills of artistic and creative activities;

- cultural, that is, there is an objective connection of a person with culture, which is presented in the form of a value system, as well as the development of a person as a creator in the development of artistic culture;

- corrective, i.e. prevention of behavior, aimed at corrective and compensatory developmental deficiencies;

formation of educational, moral-aesthetic, communicative and reflective foundations of a person, as well as encouraging his socio-cultural adaptation through art.

Art pedagogy can greatly help in achieving this result. The question remains to what extent teachers are ready to use the existing tools of artistic pedagogy. Such training implies sufficient potential for creative direction of the individual, the exploratory character of the individual's behavior in conditions of high uncertainty, the possibility to revise the stereotypes of one's experience, which is not only a professional, but also a personal development process.

At each stage of the pedagogical process, in the education of the moral qualities of elementary school students, there is an interaction of the means and technologies of artistic perception and transformation of the world with the methods and tools of moral education, which are a new, more perfect character. is enough.

REFERENCES

1. Леонтьев А.Н. Проблемы развития психики. – М.: АПН РСФСР, 1959.
2. Уматова А.У. Искусство как средство нравственного воспитания младших школьников. // Вестник ИГЛУ. - Пятигорск, 2012 - №4 - С. 237- 240. (0,25п.л.) (Входит в перечень изданий, рецензируемых ВАК РФ).
3. Е.В.Таранова., Методология артпедагогике в контексте современных междисциплинарных исследований образования.
4. Асмолов А.Г. Психология личности: Принципы общепсихологического анализа: Учебник для студ. высш. учеб. заведений. Рек. Мин. обр. РФ. — 2-е изд., перераб. / А.Г. Асмолов. М.: Смысл; Академия, 2002.
5. Насритдинова, Мадина Нуруллаевна (2022). НАУЧНО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ИСЦЕЛЕНИЯ ДЕТЕЙ С ПАТОЛОГИЕЙ, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ГИПОКСИИ, ПОСРЕДСТВОМ ИСКУССТВ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10-2), 385-393.
6. Насритдинова, М. Н. (2022). МУСИҚА ИНСОНИЯТГА НИМА УЧУН КЕРАК?. *Science and innovation*, 1(Special Issue 2), 577-580.
7. Nasritdinova, M. (2023). ARTPEDAGOGIK YONDASHUV ASOSIDA BOSHLANG'ICH SINF O'QUVCHILARINI AXLOQIY TARBIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK MODELI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(2), 199-204.
8. Насритдинова, М. (2023). ARTPEDAGOGIK YONDASHUV ASOSIDA BOLAJAK MUSIQA TA'LIMI OQITUVCHILARINING IJODKORLIK QOBILİYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DIDAKTIK TA'MINOTI. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(4), 241-246.
9. Насритдинова, М. Н. (2023). УСТОЗ МУХТОР АШРАФИЙ МАҲОРАТЛИ ПЕДАГОГ СИЙМОСИДА ШОГИРДЛАРИ ХОТИРАСИДА МАНГУ БАРҶАЁТ. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMİY JURNALI*, 3(2), 303-305.
10. Nurullayevna, N. M. Turg'unboyeva Muhlisa.(2022). THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY IN CREATING A NEW UZBEKISTAN ENLIGHTENED SOCIETY. *BEST SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH*, 1 (1), 238-241.
11. Jo'Rayev Xamidjon, & Madina Nasritdinova (2022). DOIRA CHOLG'USIDA IJO MAHORATINI YUKSALTIRISH (BOLALAR MUSIQA VA SAN'AT MAKTABLARI MISOLIDA). *Science and innovation*, 1 (C2), 26-28. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.663646
12. Мамазияев, Х. А. Ў. М., & ТАДРИЖИ, М. Ч. SAI. 2022.№ С3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ma-om-sanatida-musi-a-chol-ularining-tadrizhi> (дата обращения: 05.10. 2022).
13. Мамазияев, Хуршиджон Аъзамжон Ўғли (2022). МАҚОМ ИЖРОЧИЛИГИДА ЧОЛҒУЛАРНИНГ АЛОМАТИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10-2), 429-435.
14. X. Mamaziyaev (2022). ТЎЙ МАРОСИМ ҚЎШИҚЛАРИ (НИКОҲ ТЎЙ МАРОСИМИ ҚЎШИҚЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ). *Science and innovation*, 1 (C6), 190-199. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7178247

15. A. Abdusattorov (2022). DIMITRIY DIMITRIYEVICH SHOSTAKOVICH IJODIDA POLIFONIYA. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B6), 430-432. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7164517
16. Adiljanovna, A. M., Nurullaevna, N. M., Abdumalikovna, Y. D., Sharobidinovich, M. J., Abdujalil Abduvalio'g'li, A., & Behzod Asqaralio'g'li, T. (2021). Academic Yunus Rajabi and His Scientific Heritage. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 9092-9100.
17. Абдисатторов, А. А. Ў. (2022). БАСТАКОРЛИК ИЖОДИДА МУСИҚА ФОЛЬКЛОРИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 602-605.
18. Abdusattorov, A. About Makom Melodies Adapted for Orchestra of Uzbek Folk Instruments. *International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development*, 2(11), 28-30.
19. Murodova, D. (2021). Scientific And Theoretical Aspects of Musical Thinking. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 1(1), 196-199.
20. Murodova, D. (2021). THE CONCEPT OF MUSICAL THINKING AND ITS STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(05), 245-250.
21. Madina Nasretdinova, Ismoil Rustamov, & Oybek Karimov (2022). MUSIQA SAN'ATINING HOZIRGI KUNDAGI O'RNI. *Scientific progress*, 3 (2), 841-845.
22. Rustamov, I. (2022). DOYRA CHOLG'USIDA IJROCHILIK MAHORATINI OSHIRISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN MASHQLAR MOHIYATI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 456-460.